

Separation of Lanthanons by Paper Electrophoretic Method and Determination of Their Mobilities by the Same Technique

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Separations of, Ce(IV) from Y(III), La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) in potassium oxalate or oxalic acid; La(III) from Y(III), Dy(III); Ce(IV) from La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III); and Sm(III) from Y(III), Dy(III) in sodium acetate-sodium citrate electrolytes were successfully achieved by paper electrophoresis at low voltage.

MOBILITIES of tripositive lanthanides were calculated from their ionophoretic speeds on paper after correcting for electro-osmotic and tortuosity effects at different concentrations of hydrochloric acid as supporting electrolyte. It was found that mobilities decrease, with the increase in atomic number of the lanthanides, with the increase in strength of the supporting electrolyte, and with the decrease in ionic radii of the tripositive lanthanons. It is due to the hydrolysis of the tripositive lanthanides which increases with increasing atomic number and contraction in radii and also due to fall in conductance with increasing concentration of the supporting electrolyte.

Lanthanons and their homologues have similar mobilities and chemical properties, so their separations by electromigration are quite difficult. However, some lanthanons were separated by many workers¹⁻²⁸ by using organic acid or its salt as background electrolyte by high voltage or continuous electrophoretic technique. The authors attempted to separate lanthanons by paper electrophoresis at low voltage using different electrolytes. Only the separations of (a) Ce from Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy in 0.1N potassium oxalate (pH 7.5) or 0.1N oxalic acid in 3 hrs' run; (b) (i) La from Y and Dy, (ii) Ce from La, Pr, Nd and Sm and (iii) Sm from Y and Dy in mixed electrolyte sodium acetate-sodium citrate were successfully achieved.

Experimental

Wieland and Fischer²⁹ type horizontal electrophoretic set was used in the experiment for the separations of lanthanides. Paper strips (2 × 34 cm) from Whatman No. 1 were used as supporting medium. Potential gradient of 3 volts/cm in 0.1N potassium oxalate, 6.1 volts/cm in 0.1N oxalic acid, 2.1 volts/cm in mixed electrolytes (0.1N sodium acetate and 0.1N sodium citrate), and 4.5 volts/cm

in mixed electrolytes (0.2M lactic acid and 0.2M citric acid) were maintained in the separation of lanthanons.

Determination of Mobilities of Lanthanons :

The mobilities of tripositive lanthanides have been calculated from their ionophoretic speeds on paper after correcting for electro-osmotic and tortuosity effects at different concentrations of hydrochloric acid as supporting electrolyte.

The important factors influencing the speed of ions are: (i) electro-osmotic effect owing to the movement of the charge particles, and (ii) tortuosity factor or 'added migration path-length' owing to the winding nature of the path created by the fibrous structure of the filter paper.

Correction for electro-osmosis :

As an electro-osmotic indicator, the large polysaccharide molecules or smaller sugar molecules can be used on account of their very low mobilities in free electrophoresis at low pH.

If d_I be the distance that a migrant travels on a paper strip, measured from the origin, and d_G , the distance that an uncharged glucose molecule travels in the same direction at low pH, the net distance that the migrating ion travels is ($d_I - d_G$). The mobility U_I is expressed by :

$$U_I = \frac{d_I - d_G}{Xt} \quad \dots \quad (I)$$

where 'X' is the field strength and 't' is the time. In the same way, the speed of electro-osmotic flow may be expressed by :

$$U_{el} = \frac{d_G}{Xt} \quad \dots \quad (II)$$

From equations (I) and (II)

$$\frac{d_G}{d_I - d_G} = \frac{U_{e1}}{U_I}$$

The ratio $\frac{U_{e1}}{U_I}$ is constant regardless of distance, time or field strength, and thus $\frac{d_G}{d_I - d_G}$ or $\frac{d_I}{d_G}$ is constant.

Correction for "added migration path-length" :

The formulae employed for the determination of free solution mobilities, viz.,

$$U = \frac{dL}{dV} \quad \text{and} \quad U = \frac{DqK}{it}$$

(where, V is the voltage, L, the length of the channel, d, the distance of migration, t, the time, q, the cross sectional area, i, the current and K, the specific conductance in mho/cm) are not applicable to liquids in a highly porous supporting medium, namely, paper. It may be shown that the expression for field strength, $\frac{V}{L}$ and $\frac{i}{qK}$ are not equal, as L does not represent the true distance of voltage drop through the paper, i.e., L the length, is not the length of the channel inside the network of paper fibres, nor d the actual distance the ions move, but rather a length L' and a distance d' have to be considered.

$$\text{Since, } L' = L \left(\frac{L'}{L} \right) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\text{therefore } d' = d \left(\frac{L'}{L} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and it can be shown that

$$d = \frac{ut}{L} V \left(\frac{L'}{L} \right)^2 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Also, since in free solution the particle migrates a distance

$$d = \frac{ut}{q_a K} i \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\text{in paper this becomes } d' = \frac{ut}{q_a K} i \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where q_a is the cross-sectional area of the paper.

We have also from the previous equations (2) and (5)

$$d = \frac{ut}{q_a K} i \left(\frac{L'}{L} \right) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

that is, equations (3) and (6) differ from the free electrophoresis by the term $\left(\frac{L'}{L} \right)$, the correction

factor for calculating the mobility on paper. It was possible to determine the correction factor using $L' = Rq_a K$, where R is the resistance of the paper strip.

For the determinations of the mobilities of tri-positive lanthanides, four measurements were made under each set of experimental conditions. These included measurements of ionographic mobility and R_D , a modified R_f , as in classical chromatography of the migrant and of the electro-osmotic indicator. The general expression

$$U = \frac{U_E}{R_D^M} = \frac{U_{e1}}{R_D^{e1}}$$

were U_E denotes the ionographic mobility of the migrant and U_{e1} that of the indicator and R_D^M and R_D^{e1} , denote the R_D values of the migrant and the indicator, respectively, have been utilised for the determination of free solution mobilities of some inorganic ions. The negative sign is used in the right-hand side of this equation if the migrant is positively charged, if it is charged negatively, the positive sign is used.

Preparation of materials :

0.01 molar solutions of Rare-Earth nitrate were prepared. The background electrolytes, 0.05M, 0.1M and 0.2M hydrochloric acid (A.R.), were prepared. The reagents employed for detecting the ionic species were also prepared, viz., saturated alcoholic sodium salt of Alizarin S for Rare-Earths (colour of the band—red-violet, brown or red); 10 vol of H_2O_2 for Ce(IV) (colour of the band—brown); 2N H_2SO_4 and aniline oxalate (100 ml of 0.1N oxalic acid & 0.9 ml aniline) for glucose (colour of the band—brown).

Apparatus :

Micropipettes (1 ml capacity, graduated up to 10^{-3} ml) were used to spot a small volume of the substance under investigation on chromatographic paper. The horizontal paper electrophoretic set, which utilises the horizontal paper strips in the electrolyte saturated condition, was used with Whatman chromatographic paper no. 1.

The paper strips used are previously saturated with the relevant solvent in desiccator. There are one outlet and one inlet at the base of the chamber (Fig. 1) through which a steady stream of nitrogen gas, saturated with relevant solvent vapour, can be passed. The latter is then made gas-tight, to all intents and purposes, by placing a cover and then closing the junctions of the cover and the top of the base by means of cellophane adhesive tape. This arrangement allows the temperature of the chamber to be maintained almost constant between 29° and 31°, thus reducing evaporation of the solvent from the strips to a minimum.

Fig. 1. A=Stoppered hole for solvent addition, B=Stoppered hole for application of substance, C=Electrolyte chamber, D=Fixer plate for paper strip, E=Electrodes, F=Turning screw for fixer plate, H=Hanger for paper strips, P=Paper strips, S=Solvent vessel and I=Inlet for nitrogen.

Procedure :

To start the experiment, two strips were simultaneously used. They were moistured carefully with the electrolyte adjusted to definite pH from the ends avoiding any excess of electrolyte. They were then pressed gently between two dry filter paper sheets in order to make them, as far as possible, uniformly wet. The strips were then placed in the rack so that they were kept horizontally tant by pressing them gently between and by two glass slabs on each end inside each of the electrolyte vessels. In order that each strips might offer the same resistance towards current flow, which could be observed from the equal length of each strip exposed above the solvent level, the mid-point line of each strip was just made to touch the pointed end of a narrow plastic stick on which it rested. Electrolyte was then poured to the same level in each electrode vessel in order to avoid hydrodynamic flow of fluid in the paper, which is independent of electrical potential. The cover was then placed in position, the chamber made gas-tight and a direct current at a potential of 200 volts was applied for five minutes in order to drain out any excess of solvent. The flow of current was then carefully spotted to the marked midpoint of each of the strips. The cover was then quickly replaced and again a direct current at a potential of 200 volts was applied for half an hour. The strip was then dried and sprayed with reagent specific for the particular rare-earth ion and again dried. The distance of migration of the ion was measured as usual.

In the determination of the R_D values of the ions, two strips (50 cm x 3 cm) were simultaneously used. Each strip was marked by a pencil at two places, the first at a distance of 10 cm and the second at 13 cm from one end of the strip. The first mark was used to indicate the position of application of the substance under investigation and second for the solvent front. These measurements were used in each experiment in which R_D values were determined. The marked strips were then fixed in position to the adjustable paper-holding glass slabs, pulled horizontally tant placed inside the chamber,

below which solvent was placed in three small vessels for saturation of the strips with solvent vapour. After saturating the strips with solvent vapour, a definite volume = 300 ml of the solvent was poured in the vessel kept just below the ends of the strips through a funnel placed in the hole on the cover. The hole was closed by a soft rubber cork as soon as the solvent was poured. The solvent rose up gradually and when the solvent front reached the second mark, the same amount of the salt as used in the ionophoresis experiments, was applied on the first mark through the cork-up hole on the cover just above the second mark. The run was allowed to proceed for half an hour when appreciable movement of the solvent front took place. The strips were then taken out by removing the cover, dried and developed by the reagent specific for the particular rare-earth ion under investigation. The distance traversed by a particular ion from the first mark and that by the solvent front from the second mark were noted, and thus the R_D value for the substance was calculated.

The distance of migration, together with the R_D values were utilised for calculation of free solution mobilities.

A series of similar experiments were performed with the ions of the Rare-Earths with HCl as

Fig. 2.

electrolyte at pH values : 1.3, 1.0 and 0.69. The distances of migration of the different ions and those of glucose used as the electro-osmotic indicator in hydrochloric acid, adjusted to the above pH values, have been measured and shown in Table 1. The R_D values of these ions together with those of glycose also in hydrochloric acid at the above

TABLE 1—POTENTIAL GRADIENT=4.5 Volts/cm.
TIME=30 MINUTES, TEMPERATURE=29.31°C.
ELECTROLYTIC MEDIUM=HCl OF DIFFERENT
CONCENTRATIONS

Migrant	Distance of migration in cm.		
	0.05M HCl (pH=1.3)	0.1M HCl (pH=1)	0.2M HCl (pH=0.69)
Glucose	0.7	0.7	0.7
La ³⁺	3.0	2.5	2.0
Ce ⁴⁺	1.5	1.3	1.0
Pr ³⁺	2.8	2.3	1.8
Nd ³⁺	2.6	2.1	1.6
Sm ³⁺	2.6	2.0	1.6
Eu ³⁺	2.5	2.0	1.5
Gd ³⁺	2.4	2.0	1.5
Tb ³⁺	2.4	1.8	1.4
Dy ³⁺	2.3	1.8	1.3
Ho ³⁺	2.4	1.9	1.3
Er ³⁺	2.2	1.7	1.2
Yb ³⁺	2.2	1.7	1.2
Lu ³⁺	2.0	1.5	1.0

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF ' R_D ' VALUES IN
HYDROCHLORIC ACID OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Substance	0.05M HCl (pH=1.3)	0.1M HCl (pH=1)	0.2M HCl (pH=0.69)
Glucose	0.90	0.92	0.95
La ³⁺	0.97	0.95	0.98
Ce ⁴⁺	0.98	0.98	0.99
Pr ³⁺	0.97	0.98	0.99
Nd ³⁺	0.95	0.97	0.98
Sm ³⁺	1.00	0.96	1.00
Eu ³⁺	0.99	0.99	1.00
Gd ³⁺	0.95	0.99	1.00
Tb ³⁺	0.97	0.98	0.99
Dy ³⁺	0.95	0.99	0.99
Ho ³⁺	0.99	0.99	0.99
Er ³⁺	0.95	0.98	0.98
Yb ³⁺	0.99	1.00	1.00
Lu ³⁺	0.99	1.00	1.00

TABLE 3A—VARIATION OF MOBILITY OF IONS WITH
CHANGE OF CONCENTRATION OF ELECTROLYTE

Migrant	0.05M HCl Mobility × 10 ⁴ cm ² /volt-sec. (Observed)	0.1M HCl Mobility × 10 ⁴ cm ² /volt-sec. (Observed)	0.2M HCl Mobility × 10 ⁴ cm ² /volt-sec. (Observed)
Glucose	0.8642	0.8642	0.8642
La ³⁺	3.703	3.086	2.469
Ce ⁴⁺	1.852	1.603	1.234
Pr ³⁺	3.452	2.839	2.222
Nd ³⁺	3.210	2.592	1.975
Sm ³⁺	3.210	2.469	1.975
Eu ³⁺	3.086	2.469	1.852
Gd ³⁺	2.963	2.469	1.852
Tb ³⁺	2.963	2.222	1.728
Dy ³⁺	2.839	2.222	1.604
Ho ³⁺	2.963	2.346	1.604
Er ³⁺	2.716	2.098	1.481
Yb ³⁺	2.716	2.098	1.481
Lu ³⁺	2.469	1.852	1.234

TABLE 3B

Migrant	Atomic number	Ionic radii M ³⁺ (°A)	0.05M HCl Mobility × 10 ⁴ (cm ² /volt- sec) (Com- pound)	0.1M HCl Mobility × 10 ⁴ (cm ² /volt- sec) (Com- pound)	0.2M HCl Mobility × 10 ⁴ (cm ² /volt-sec) (Compound)
La ³⁺	57	1.061	2.86	2.31	1.61
Ce ⁴⁺	58	—	0.93	0.70	0.34
Pr ³⁺	59	1.010	2.60	1.96	1.34
Nd ³⁺	60	0.995	2.42	1.73	1.11
Sm ³⁺	62	0.964	2.25	1.63	1.06
Eu ³⁺	63	0.950	2.16	1.55	0.94
Gd ³⁺	64	0.938	2.16	1.55	0.94
Tb ³⁺	65	0.923	2.09	1.34	0.84
Dy ³⁺	66	0.908	2.03	1.31	0.71
Ho ³⁺	67	0.894	2.03	1.33	0.71
Er ³⁺	68	0.881	1.87	1.20	0.60
Yb ³⁺	70	0.858	1.78	1.16	0.57
Lu ³⁺	71	0.848	1.53	0.91	0.32

mentioned pH values are given in Table 2. The observed mobilities and computed free solution mobilities (in terms of cm²/volt-sec) of the ions under investigation are given in Tables 3A and 3B, and represented graphically in Fig. 2 as function of ionic radii.

Discussion

It is seen from Tables 3A and 3B and Fig. 1 that mobilities decrease, with the increase in atomic number, with the increase in strength of the electrolyte, and, with the decrease in ionic radii. The reason for the low mobility of the tripositive lanthanide ions at the lower strengths of hydrochloric acid is due to their hydrolysis.

The M³⁺ aquo ions are hydrolysed³⁰ according to $M(H_2O)_n^{3+} + H_2O = M(H_2O)_{n-1}(OH)^{2+} + H_3O^+$ and the tendency to hydrolysis increases with increasing atomic number as would be expected from contraction in radii.

The smallest ion, Lu³⁺, should have the largest mobility, but it actually has the lowest in the series. This discrepancy can be explained as:—the ions are attached in solution to a number of water molecules, and these "hydrated ions" migrate as a whole under the influence of the applied potential gradient. If the lanthanum ion is more highly hydrated than praseodymium, and so on through the series, the size of the ion-hydrated complex may decrease in going from lanthanum to lutecium. In view of the high polarizing power of a small ion, it is probable that the attraction between the ions and the molecular dipoles of water will decrease steadily with increasing atomic weight, as required to account for the observed ionic mobilities.

So, due to hydrolysis the sizes of the ions increase with increasing atomic number, and as a result the mobilities decrease sharply, Ce⁴⁺ ion has much lower mobilities, because the very highly charged Ce⁴⁺ ion has a pronounced tendency to

hydrate³⁰ and the hydrate ion, $Ce(H_2O)_n^{4+}$, is a strong acid.

Again the mobility of an ion decreases with increasing electrolyte concentration due mainly to the falling off in conductance with increasing concentration. In more strong electrolyte, the electrostatic attraction between positive and negative ion persists, i.e., there may be a definite pairing of ions or a continual interchange of partners between ion-pairs. The consequence of this is that although ionization may be complete, dissociation will be incomplete except in very dilute electrolyte. The quantity of electricity that can pass through an electrolyte, and hence its conductance, depends on the product of the number of ions, the charge carried by each ion, and the velocity with which the ions move. Since the total charge is a constant in each case, the conductance of an electrolyte can only depend on the speeds of the ions. So, as the conductance falls with increasing concentration of the electrolyte, the mobility of an ion falls.

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